

Polarographic Investigation of the Composition and Stability of the Complexes of Cadmium and Lead with Hippuric Acid

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In continuation of our previous work¹⁻⁶ polarographic investigations on the complexes of cadmium and lead ion with hippurate are reported in this communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used were of reagent grade purity. Solutions of lead nitrate and cadmium nitrate were prepared in double distilled water. Potassium nitrate was used to keep the ionic strength constant (1.0). 0.001% Gelatin was used as maxima suppressor. Purified Hydrogen was used for deaeration of the solutions.

Sodium hippurate was used as a complexing agent. Manual polarograph with scalamp galvanometer as current recorder was used in all the determinations. Measurements of half wave potentials were made against S.C.E. The conventional H-Type cell with agar-agar bridge saturated with potassium chloride was used. Temperature was maintained at $28 \pm 1^\circ$.

The composition and formation constants of the complexes were evaluated graphically following DeFord and Hume's method⁷.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Cadmium Hippurate System : A single well defined reduction wave was obtained for each solution. A shift in half wave potential towards more negative side as well as a decrease in diffusion current with increasing ligand concentration was observed. Plots of $\log i/i_d - i$ vs. $E_{a,e}$ were found to be linear with a slope of 31 ± 2 mV thus indicating a reversible process with two electron reduction. A curve was obtained when a plot of $-\log Cx$ and half wave potentials was made indicating thereby the formation of more than one complex. The experimentally determined values of E_1 together with $F_j(X)$ ⁷ values are given in Table I.

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It is assumed that ionic atmosphere changes little and therefore the activity coefficient⁵ probably changes very little. As $F_2(X)$ was independent of ligand concentration, two complexes were present $\text{Cd}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CONHCH}_2\text{COO})^+$, $\text{Cd}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CONHCH}_2\text{COO})_2$. The values of the formation constants of the two complex species were found to be 9 and 23 ± 3 respectively.

TABLE 1

Cd²⁺ Hippurate System $\text{Cd}^{2+} = 1\text{mM}$ $\mu = 1(\text{KNO}_3)$, Temp. = 29°C.

Conc. of ligand	id in div.	$-E_i$ vs S.C.E.	Slope of "log plot"	$F_0(X)$	$F_1(X)$	$F_2(X)$
0.00M	66.0	0.575 V	31 mV	—	—	—
0.05M	64.0	0.5787 V	32 mV	1.370	7.4	—
0.10M	61.6	0.5850 V	31 mV	2.331	13.31	—
0.15M	59.5	0.5887 V	30 mV	3.170	14.46	—
0.20M	57.5	0.5900 V	32 mV	3.625	13.12	28
0.30M	54.5	0.5950 V	31 mV	5.610	15.36	26.22
0.40M	52.5	0.6000 V	32 mV	8.508	18.77	29.4
0.50M	51.5	0.6030 V	30 mV	10.91	19.82	24.6
0.60M	49.5	0.6075 V	31 mV	16.16	25.16	29
0.70M	47.0	0.6100 V	30 mV	20.53	27.9	29.4
0.80M	46.0	0.6125 V	32 mV	25.34	30.72	28

$$\beta_1 = K_1 = 9\dots;$$

$$\beta_2 = K_1K_2 = 28\dots; \quad (K_2 = 3.11)$$

Lead Hippurate System: The reduction wave obtained in each case is a single and a well defined one. Shift in half wave potential is observed with increase in hippurate ion concentration and a decrease in diffusion current is also noted $\log i/i_d - i$ vs. $E_{d,e}$ plots were found to be linear with a slope of 31±2 mV corresponding to a two electron reduction.

The plot of $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ vs $-\log C_x$ gives a curve instead of a straight line proving thereby the formation of more than one complex. Plots of $F_J(X)$ functions are shown in Fig. 2. The above results show the formation of the following complex ions. $\text{Pb}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CONHCH}_2\text{COO})^+$ and $\text{Pb}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CONHCH}_2\text{COO})_2$. The overall formation constants are found to be 11 and 45 ± 5 respectively.

TABLE 2

Pb²⁺ Hippurate System

$\text{Pb}^{2+} = 1 \text{ mM}$, $\mu = 1(\text{KNO}_3)$, Temp. 29°

Conc. of ligand	id in div.	$-E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ vs SCE	Slope of log plot	$F_0(X)$	$F_1(X)$	$F_2(X)$
0.00 M	36	0.4025	30 mV	—	—	—
0.10 M	30.5	0.4150	30 mV	3.024	20.24	—
0.20 M	28.25	0.4250	31 mV	6.745	28.72	—
0.30 M	27.0	0.4287	32 mV	9.656	28.85	49.5
0.40 M	24.0	0.4350	30 mV	7.80	33.6	49.0
0.50 M	23.0	0.4400	31 mV	—	—	—
0.60 M	22.0	0.4425	32 mV	3.64	46.62	54.0

$$K_1 = 11, \quad = K_1 K_2 = 45 \pm 5$$

In both the cases the observed trend $K_1 > K_2$ is what is usually observed in most systems due to statistical and saturation effects.

TABLE 3

Height	h_{eff} in cms	id in μ A	id/ $h^{\frac{1}{2}}_{eff}$
60	58.716	7.02	0.9162
55	53.716	6.75	0.9210
50	58.716	6.413	0.9190

The results in Table 3 & 4 obviously indicate that the limiting current for both cadmium and lead Hippurate are diffusion controlled.

TABLE 4

Height	h_{eff}	id in μ A	id/ $h^{\frac{1}{2}}_{eff}$
65	63.716	5.643	0.7070
60	58.716	5.423	0.7079
55	53.716	5.229	0.7135

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